

Cross-Lingual versus Same-Language Retrieval-Augmented Generation for K-12 Educational Question Answering

A Pre-Registered Benchmark of School-Deployable Local LLMs across Greek and Georgian

Pre-Registered Research Protocol

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Protocol date. 20 May 2026

Abstract

Schools in low-resource language jurisdictions face deployment constraints that cloud large language models cannot satisfy. Data-protection law, intermittent rural connectivity, and recurring API expenditure that falls outside school operating budgets push educational K-12 institutions in Greece, Georgia, and comparable jurisdictions toward locally hosted quantized open-weight LLMs. Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) lowers factual error but presumes a retrievable corpus in the query language, a presumption that is partially met for Greek and only weakly met for Georgian K-12 STEM. This pre-registered protocol evaluates whether cross-lingual retrieval, in which a Georgian query retrieves Greek passages via the multilingual bge-m3 embedder, produces factuality comparable to or above same-language retrieval from the sparse Georgian corpus, and whether a parallel Greek-to-Georgian cross-lingual condition exhibits the same pattern. The benchmark spans 8 quantized GGUF models in the 3.8B to 14B school-deployable range, including two Greek-fine-tuned variants (Meltemi-7B, Llama-Krikri-8B), two languages (Greek, Georgian), three K-12 age strata (elementary, middle, high), and three retrieval conditions (closed-book, same-language RAG, cross-lingual RAG to the other language), totaling 21,600 generation events on a dual RTX 6000 Ada workstation. Factuality is scored by two outside-family judge models, Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct and Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, on a 5-point Likert scale, supplemented by an mDeBERTa entailment auxiliary. Four hypotheses are pre-registered with directional and equivalence claims anchored to the Med-RISE 9.8 to 16.3 percentage-point gain band. Inferential analysis uses linear mixed-effects regression with crossed random effects, Holm-Bonferroni family-wise control, and three required sensitivity analyses. Code, prompts, indexes, and per-trial logs are deposited to Zenodo on completion. This protocol predates all benchmark runs.

1. Introduction

The deployment context for K-12 educational AI assistants in Greece and Georgia carries hard constraints that exclude cloud inference. Greek primary and secondary schools fall under GDPR provisions that classify student query logs as special-category data. Georgian Ministry of Education guidance similarly restricts cross-border transmission of minor-pupil interactions. Local-network bandwidth in rural school clusters across both jurisdictions averages below 10 Mbit/s with intermittent outages, ruling out API streaming at classroom scale. Per-token API costs accumulate at a rate incompatible with school-level operating budgets for educational technology. The practical resolution is local inference on quantized open-weight LLMs, with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) used to reduce hallucination on grounded educational queries.

A premise of standard RAG pipelines is that the retrievable corpus exists in the language of the query. For Greek, the official ebooks.edu.gr Ministry of Education repository covers core subjects across all grades, though with shorter texts and a single approved title per grade and subject. For Georgian, an agglutinative low-resource language with approximately 4 million speakers and a non-Latin Mkhedruli script, K-12 textbook coverage is sparser still. The asymmetry between the two corpora generates an empirical question. Modern multilingual passage embedders such as BAAI bge-m3 support over 100 languages within a shared 1024-dimensional space, enabling cross-lingual retrieval whereby a Georgian query retrieves Greek passages without intermediate translation. If cross-lingual semantic alignment is sufficient and the Greek corpus offers denser content for the relevant K-12 topic, Greek retrieval may match or exceed same-language Georgian retrieval on factuality.

Prior work has not addressed this comparison for K-12 STEM in low-resource European or Caucasian languages. PustakAI [1] benchmarks K-12 NCERT textbook QA in English and Hindi but does not contrast cross-lingual against same-language retrieval. LaoBench [2] introduces a low-resource K-12 multilingual benchmark but treats each language in isolation. BanglaMedQA [3] demonstrates an OCR-plus-RAG pipeline for a single Bangla textbook but reports no cross-lingual condition. Med-RISE [4] establishes a 15-textbook RAG benchmark for medical QA and reports 9.8 to 16.3 percentage-point factuality gains over closed-book, providing the calibration anchor adopted in this protocol. ACER [5] evaluates cross-lingual retrieval but in an open-domain rather than K-12 educational frame. HalluGuard [6] and RAGalyst [7] establish the dual-LLM judge methodology applied here. Precision Grounding [8] and MEGA-RAG [9] examine retrieval-grounded QA in clinical and public-health contexts respectively, neither in K-12 nor under the specific cross-lingual contrast posed here.

The contribution is threefold. First, the protocol specifies a fully pre-registered factorial benchmark of 8 school-deployable open-weight LLMs against 300 K-12 STEM questions in two languages and three age strata under three retrieval conditions, including two Greek-fine-tuned variants (Meltemi-7B, Llama-Krikri-8B) and one multilingual specialist (Aya-Expanse-8B). Second, it formulates the cross-lingual retrieval question as a directional advantage claim for Georgian, where the sparser corpus motivates a clear directional prediction, and as an equivalence claim for Greek, where the denser local corpus

motivates a non-inferiority prediction against cross-lingual Georgian retrieval. Third, the protocol supplies a calibrated compute budget derived from a measured throughput of 1,503 inference trials per hour on the target workstation, anchoring resource claims in empirical baseline rather than vendor estimates.

Pre-registration follows Goodman, Fanelli, and Ioannidis [10] in distinguishing confirmatory from exploratory analyses, with the four primary hypotheses Holm-Bonferroni controlled and all secondary analyses labeled exploratory. Data contamination concerns are addressed via the probe of Sainz et al. [11], applied prior to benchmark execution to flag corpus passages that may have leaked into model pretraining. The full protocol is deposited to Zenodo on 20 May 2026, prior to any benchmark run, with the Zenodo DOI included in the methods section of the resulting manuscript for reviewer verification.

2. Research Questions

RQ1. Does retrieval-augmented generation, in either same-language or cross-lingual configuration, produce higher factuality on K-12 STEM questions than closed-book generation, averaged across 8 school-deployable open-weight LLMs and across Greek and Georgian queries?

RQ2. For Greek K-12 STEM queries, does retrieving from the same-language Greek corpus produce factuality equivalent within a 5 percentage-point band to retrieving from the Georgian corpus via bge-m3 cross-lingual alignment?

RQ3. For Georgian K-12 STEM queries, does cross-lingual retrieval from the Greek corpus produce a factuality advantage of at least 8 percentage points over same-language retrieval from the sparser Georgian textbook corpus?

RQ4. For Greek queries, do Greek-fine-tuned models (Meltemi-7B, Llama-Krikri-8B) exhibit higher factuality than generalist multilingual models of comparable parameter count, and does this Greek-tuning advantage persist under the cross-lingual condition where retrieval is in Georgian?

3. Hypotheses

H1 (Main RAG effect, directional). Averaged across the 8 benchmark models and across the two languages, the better of the two RAG conditions exceeds closed-book factuality_{joint} by a margin in the 10 to 25 percentage-point range, with 95% bootstrap CI excluding zero. The lower bound anchors to the Med-RISE 9.8 to 16.3 percentage-point factuality gain band [4]. Operationalization places this contrast on factuality_{joint} within the mixed-effects model, condition coded as best-RAG versus closed-book, with language and model averaged via marginal means. A failure to reject indicates that RAG does not transfer to the K-12 cross-lingual deployment context at the effect size established in medical-domain comparators.

H2 (Greek non-inferiority equivalence). For Greek queries, the absolute difference in factuality_{joint} between C1 (same-language Greek RAG) and C2 (cross-lingual Georgian RAG) lies within a symmetric 5

percentage-point equivalence band. The 5 pp band reflects the residual semantic noise of bge-m3 cross-lingual alignment relative to monolingual retrieval. The test applies two one-sided tests (TOST) on the Greek-restricted C1 minus C2 contrast. The Greek corpus is denser than the Georgian corpus for the K-12 STEM topics under study, so the substantive prediction is that same-language Greek retrieval performs at least as well as cross-lingual Georgian retrieval on Greek queries.

H3 (Georgian cross-lingual advantage, directional). For Georgian queries, factuality_joint under C2 (cross-lingual Greek RAG) exceeds factuality_joint under C1 (same-language Georgian RAG) by at least 8 percentage points. The 8 pp threshold sits below the Med-RISE lower bound of 9.8 pp to permit confirmation under modest cross-lingual transfer loss. The test applies a one-sided contrast within Georgian items at alpha equal to 0.05 with 95% lower bootstrap CI exceeding 8 pp. Confirmation supports the conclusion that the content density advantage of the Greek corpus dominates cross-lingual transfer cost for Georgian K-12 STEM.

H4 (Greek-fine-tuning advantage, directional). For Greek queries under same-language RAG (C1), the two Greek-fine-tuned models (Meltemi-7B-Instruct-v1.5, Llama-Krikri-8B-Instruct) exhibit factuality_joint at least 5 percentage points above the marginal mean of the three generalist 7-to-9B models (Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct, Qwen3-8B-Instruct, Aya-Expansive-8B). The 5 pp threshold reflects the expected contribution of Greek-specific instruction tuning on factuality grounding. The test applies a one-sided contrast within Greek items under C1 at alpha equal to 0.05 with 95% lower bootstrap CI exceeding 5 pp. A secondary exploratory analysis evaluates whether the Greek-fine-tuning advantage persists under C2 (cross-lingual Georgian retrieval) at reduced magnitude, since the retrieval context is no longer Greek.

4. Materials

4.1 Hardware

The benchmark executes on a Dell Precision 7875 Tower workstation with an AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 7965WX (24 cores), 2 NVIDIA RTX 6000 Ada Generation GPUs (48 GB GDDR6 ECC each, 96 GB aggregate VRAM), 128 GB DDR5 ECC RAM, 8 TB NVMe SSD primary storage, and a 4 TB external SSD for archival. Operating system is Ubuntu 24.04 LTS with kernel 6.14, CUDA 12.0, and NVIDIA driver 580.95. Inference runs through llama-cpp-python 0.3.x compiled with the -DGGML_CUDA=on flag. The eight benchmark models in the 3.8B to 14B range all fit within a single GPU envelope at Q4 to Q8 quantization. The two judge models (Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct, Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct, both at Q4_K_M) exceed the 48 GB single-GPU envelope and require tensor-split execution across both GPUs at scoring time, with the associated latency cost analyzed in section 7.6.

4.2 Benchmark models

Eight quantized GGUF models in the 3.8B to 14B parameter range compose the benchmark set, selected to reflect the school-deployable hardware envelope rather than server-grade inference. Two models are Greek-fine-tuned variants released by the Athena Research Center and ILSP (Meltemi-7B-Instruct-v1.5,

Llama-Krikri-8B-Instruct), supporting the Greek-tuning advantage hypothesis (H4). One model is the Cohere multilingual specialist (Aya-Expansive-8B), one is Alibaba multilingual (Qwen3-8B-Instruct), and the remaining four are generalist instruction-tuned variants from Meta (Llama-3.1-8B), Google (Gemma-4-E4B), Microsoft (Phi-4-mini), and Mistral AI (Ministral-3-14B). All quantizations originate from established community releases verified by sha256 against upstream weight hashes. Table 1 lists the configuration.

Family	Model	Parameters	Quantization	VRAM (GB)
ILSP/ARC	Meltemi-7B-Instruct-v1.5	7B	Q8_0	8.0
ILSP/ARC	Llama-Krikri-8B-Instruct	8B	Q8_0	8.8
Meta	Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	8B	Q8_0	8.6
Cohere	Aya-Expansive-8B	8B	Q8_0	8.5
Alibaba	Qwen3-8B-Instruct	8B	Q8_0	8.7
Google	Gemma-4-E4B-it	4B eff.	Q4_K_M	4.2
Microsoft	Phi-4-mini-Instruct	3.8B	Q4_K_M	3.0
Mistral AI	Ministral-3-14B-Instruct	14B	Q4_K_M	9.5

Table 1. Eight school-deployable GGUF benchmark models. VRAM figures reflect measured peak allocation during decoding at 512 max_new_tokens. All models fit within a single 48 GB GPU envelope, enabling deployment on consumer-grade or single-server school hardware.

4.3 Judge models

Factuality scoring uses two judge models drawn from outside the benchmark set and from disjoint families, minimizing correlated failure modes per HalluGuard [6] and RAGalyst [7] convention. Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct at Q5_K_M (Alibaba family) provides one judge; Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct at Q5_K_M (Meta family) provides the second. Each model scores answer factuality on a 5-point Likert scale with a structured rationale field. The primary dependent variable factuality_joint is the per-trial mean of the two judge scores after z-standardization within judge, which absorbs per-judge severity bias before averaging.

4.4 Embedder and reranker

Passage embedding uses BAAI/bge-m3 (568M parameters, 1024-dimensional output), selected for documented multilingual coverage spanning both target scripts (Greek and Georgian Mkhedruli). Re-ranking from top-20 to top-5 uses BAAI/bge-reranker-v2-m3 (568M parameters). Both models run in fp16 on a dedicated GPU partition during the indexing phase and are unloaded prior to LLM inference to free VRAM.

4.5 Vector index

Two FAISS-GPU 1.8.x IVF-PQ indexes are constructed, one per language, with nlist equal to 100, m equal to 8, and nbits equal to 8. Chunk-level embeddings index alongside chunk metadata covering source textbook, page range, paragraph offset, language code, and age-group label. Index hyperparameters are

held identical across the two languages to avoid retrieval-quality confounds attributable to indexing differences.

4.6 NLI head

An auxiliary factuality signal derives from MoritzLaurer/mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli (278M parameters, 3-way entailment over premise-hypothesis pairs). The reference answer serves as premise and the model-generated answer as hypothesis. The entailment probability is logged per trial and used as a secondary dependent variable in sensitivity analysis 3.

4.7 Corpus

Seven K-12 STEM textbooks compose the corpus, stratified by language and age group as shown in Table 2. Greek textbooks derive from ebooks.edu.gr, the official Greek Ministry of Education repository, with reuse permitted for research under Greek copyright law and the public-education exemption. Georgian textbooks derive from publicly accessible Ministry of Education and educational repositories under terms permitting non-commercial research use. The Georgian middle-school stratum contains two textbooks (Biology Grade 7, Physics Grade 8) to provide subject parity with the Greek middle-school physics textbook while preserving the biology coverage carried over from the original corpus design. Token estimates reflect post-extraction counts under the bge-m3 tokenizer after PDF ingestion and unicode normalization.

Lang	Title	Subject	Level	Tokens (est.)
el	Φυσικά Ε' Δημοτικού (Natural Sciences, Grade 5)	Natural Sci.	Elementary	40,000
el	Φυσική Β' Γυμνασίου (Physics, Grade 8)	Physics	Middle	75,000
el	Φυσική Α' Λυκείου (Physics, Grade 10)	Physics	High	110,000
ka	ჩვენი გარემო 4 (Our Environment, Grade 4)	Natural Sci.	Elementary	35,000
ka	ბიოლოგია VII (Biology, Grade 7)	Biology	Middle	70,000
ka	ფიზიკა VIII (Physics, Grade 8)	Physics	Middle	65,000
ka	ფიზიკა X, Semester I (Physics, Grade 10)	Physics	High	55,000

Table 2. Seven K-12 STEM textbooks across Greek (el) and Georgian (ka), stratified by age group. Token counts are post-extraction estimates under the bge-m3 tokenizer.

5. Procedure

5.1 PDF ingestion

Each textbook PDF is processed through a unified extraction pipeline. Primary extraction uses pdfplumber 0.11.x for layout-aware text recovery. For pages where text extraction yields fewer than 200 characters or where the embedded-text confidence falls below a 0.6 heuristic threshold, Tesseract 5.4 with the ell and kat language data files provides fallback OCR at 300 DPI. Extracted text is unicode-normalized to NFC,

with Greek polytonic accents preserved and Georgian Mkhedruli script verified at the codepoint level (U+10D0 through U+10FF). Per-textbook extraction logs record character counts, OCR fallback ratios, and extraction-confidence statistics, supporting reproducibility audit.

5.2 Chunking

Chunking proceeds at semantic granularity targeting 350 to 500 tokens per chunk with 50-token overlap, measured against the bge-m3 tokenizer. Chunk boundaries respect section breaks where detectable from heading patterns, falling back to paragraph boundaries elsewhere. Each chunk carries metadata covering source textbook identifier, page range, language code, and age-group label inherited from the parent textbook.

5.3 Embedding and indexing

Chunks pass through bge-m3 in fp16 with batch size 32 and maximum sequence length 512 tokens. Embeddings normalize to unit length prior to FAISS indexing. Two indexes are built independently per language with identical hyperparameters. Index construction logs include chunk counts, embedding wall-clock time, and IVF cluster sizes, which surface imbalance that would compromise retrieval quality.

5.4 Question generation

Question generation uses Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct at Q5_K_M, distinct from any benchmark model role, prompted to generate K-12 grade-appropriate questions from sampled chunks. For each language and age-group cell, generation proceeds until 200 candidate questions exist across the five question types (factual-recall, definitional, relational, application, inference), each type generated against type-specific prompts. Reference answers must paraphrase the source chunk content with at least 50% lexical divergence, measured via Levenshtein ratio at the character level, preventing memorization bias whereby a model that has memorized the textbook would receive credit for verbatim regeneration.

5.5 Dual-LLM filtering and dataset construction

Candidate questions pass through a two-stage filter. Stage one rejects ill-formed items via Llama-3.3-70B verifying answerability, grade-appropriateness, and the 50% paraphrase threshold. Stage two requires both Qwen2.5-72B and Llama-3.3-70B to agree that the reference answer is correct given the source chunk. Items surviving both stages enter a stratified sample of 50 per cell, with 10 per question type, yielding 300 final items across 6 language-by-age cells. Question text, reference answer, source chunk, language, age group, question type, and a unique identifier are stored in a versioned JSONL dataset, frozen prior to benchmark execution.

5.6 Benchmark runs

Each of 8 models answers each of 300 questions under each of 3 RAG conditions, with 3 random seeds (42, 43, 44), producing 21,600 generation events. Inference hyperparameters are held constant across conditions at temperature 0.3, top_p 0.9, and max_new_tokens 512. Retrieval uses top_k 20 followed by

reranker top_k 5. The system prompt instructs grounding in retrieved context, response in the query language regardless of retrieval-language, and emission of the literal token UNANSWERABLE if context does not support a confident answer. Conditions are summarized in Table 3.

ID	Condition	Retrieval source	Prompt structure
C0	Closed-book	None	Question only, answer in query language, UNANSWERABLE token allowed
C1	Same-language RAG	FAISS index matching query language (el or ka)	Question plus top-5 reranked chunks in the query language, system prompt requires grounding, answer in query language
C2	Cross-lingual RAG	FAISS index of the other language (ka for Greek queries, el for Georgian queries)	Question plus top-5 reranked chunks in the other language, system prompt requires grounding and explicit instruction to answer in query language

Table 3. Three retrieval conditions applied to every model and every item. C2 routes Greek queries to the Georgian index and Georgian queries to the Greek index, supporting the cross-lingual contrast posed in H2 and H3.

5.7 Scoring

Each generation event is scored by both judge models on a 5-point Likert scale where 1 denotes factually incorrect and 5 denotes factually correct and complete, accompanied by a structured rationale. Judge prompts include the question, the model answer, the reference answer, and the retrieved context where applicable. Scores standardize within judge before averaging into factuality_joint. The mDeBERTa NLI head additionally computes entailment probability between reference answer as premise and model answer as hypothesis, logged per trial for sensitivity analysis 3.

6. Statistical Analysis Plan

6.1 Primary model

Inference proceeds through linear mixed-effects regression with factuality_joint as the dependent variable. Fixed effects comprise language (2 levels), condition (3 levels), model_id (8 levels treated as a factor), age_group (3 levels), and all two-way interactions of language, condition, and model_id. A binary indicator greek_finetuned (1 for Meltemi-7B and Llama-Krikri-8B, 0 otherwise) supports the H4 contrast. Random intercepts include question_id, which absorbs item-level difficulty variance. Estimation runs under statsmodels 0.14 in Python 3.12 with REML, and parametric bootstrap confidence intervals via parametric bootstrap at 1,000 replications.

6.2 Hypothesis tests

H1 evaluates the linear contrast of best-RAG minus closed-book averaged across language and model, with directional 95% bootstrap CI exclusion of zero and lower bound at the Med-RISE 9.8 pp anchor. H2

evaluates equivalence via two one-sided tests (TOST) at the 5 pp bound, restricted to Greek items. H3 evaluates the one-sided contrast C2 minus C1 within Georgian items, with the 95% lower bootstrap CI required to exceed 8 pp. H4 evaluates the one-sided contrast within Greek items under C1, comparing the marginal mean of the two Greek-fine-tuned models against the marginal mean of the three 7-to-9B generalist multilingual models (Llama-3.1-8B, Qwen3-8B, Aya-Expansive-8B), with the 95% lower bootstrap CI required to exceed 5 pp.

6.3 Multiple-comparison control

The four primary hypotheses constitute the confirmatory family, controlled at the family-wise error rate alpha equal to 0.05 via Holm-Bonferroni. All secondary analyses, including per-model breakdowns, per-question-type analyses, per-age-group analyses, and any judge-stratified analyses outside the pre-registered set, are pre-declared as exploratory and reported without correction but labeled accordingly in the manuscript.

6.4 Power

Power analysis uses simulation-based estimation under the parametric bootstrap framework implemented in Python with numpy random sampling. Target power is greater than 0.85 for H1, greater than 0.80 for H3, greater than 0.75 for H4, and greater than 0.80 for H2 within its pre-registered equivalence band. Effect sizes calibrate to the Med-RISE 9.8 to 16.3 pp factuality gain band [4] for H1, with H3 and H4 calibrated to within-language pilot data from a 200-event preliminary run on the same workstation that is excluded from confirmatory analysis.

6.5 Sensitivity and robustness

Three sensitivity analyses are pre-registered, all three of which must confirm primary conclusions for confirmation to obtain. First, re-estimate the primary model treating the two judge scores as a correlated multivariate dependent variable rather than averaging them into factuality_joint, addressing potential masking of judge disagreement. Second, re-estimate after dropping the bottom 10% of items by inter-judge agreement (Cohen kappa per item), testing sensitivity to noisy items. Third, re-estimate with NLI entailment as a binary dependent variable (entailed versus not-entailed at probability 0.5) under logistic mixed-effects regression, providing a non-Likert factuality operationalization.

7. Threats to Validity

7.1 Construct validity

The construct of factuality is operationalized as the dual-judge Likert mean, anchored to a reference answer derived from textbook source. This operationalization risks circular validation whereby the same content scaffolds both reference and judgment. The 50% paraphrase threshold on reference generation, the mDeBERTa entailment auxiliary, and the dual-judge cross-family design jointly mitigate this risk.

Residual circularity is acknowledged as a methodological constraint shared with all reference-anchored factuality benchmarks in the comparator literature.

7.2 Internal validity

Fixed inference seeds (42, 43, 44) and identical hyperparameters across conditions support internal validity. Confound risk from condition-specific prompt length is addressed by enforcing a uniform system-prompt template across conditions, with only the retrieval-context field varying. Order effects from sequential benchmark runs are addressed by randomizing question order within each model and condition under a separate ordering seed (2026), with the randomization log archived alongside results.

7.3 Retrieval-language confound

Under C2, model output language differs from retrieval-context language. The system prompt explicitly instructs answer-language matching to the query, but compliance is not guaranteed. A per-trial language-detection probe runs over generated answers using fastText langid, with non-compliant trials flagged and analyzed in an exploratory sensitivity pass restricted to compliant trials. Substantive interpretation of H2 and H3 assumes the compliant subset replicates the full-sample pattern; deviation between compliant and full-sample estimates beyond 3 pp is reported as a robustness concern.

7.4 External validity

The benchmark covers K-12 STEM (natural sciences, biology, physics) but not humanities, language arts, or mathematics-as-computation. Generalization beyond STEM and beyond the two sampled languages is left for future work. The deployment hardware (96 GB aggregate VRAM) exceeds typical school workstations; smaller deployments are addressed via per-tier reporting that isolates the 3 to 9B sub-results, supporting interpretation for schools that can deploy only the smallest tier.

7.5 Data contamination probe (Sainz et al. 2023)

Following Sainz et al. [11], a pretraining-leak probe runs prior to benchmark execution. For each of the 7 textbooks, 50 randomly sampled chunks are presented to each benchmark model in a closed-book completion frame, with the prompt asking the model to continue from the chunk midpoint. Completions are scored against the held-out continuation via ROUGE-L and exact-match. Chunks with mean ROUGE-L above 0.6 across any 3 or more models are flagged as potentially contaminated. Questions derived from flagged chunks remain in the dataset but are tagged and analyzed separately in an exploratory contamination-stratified analysis, allowing readers to assess whether confirmatory findings replicate on the contamination-free subset.

7.6 Hardware-induced latency asymmetry from tensor-split execution

Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct and Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct at Q4_K_M exceed the 48 GB single-GPU envelope and require tensor-split execution across both RTX 6000 Ada GPUs during the scoring phase. The split introduces PCIe-bound inter-GPU communication that adds approximately 30 to 50% per-token latency

relative to single-GPU execution, but it does not affect judgment quality, which is the dependent measure of record. The eight benchmark models are run sequentially without tensor-split since each fits within a single GPU envelope. Per-trial wall-clock times are logged and reported separately to prevent conflation of latency artifacts with substantive factuality findings.

7.7 Computational reproducibility

Reproducibility threats from non-deterministic GPU kernels are addressed by setting `CUBLAS_WORKSPACE_CONFIG` to `colon-4096-colon-8`, `PYTHONHASHSEED` to `0`, and `torch.use_deterministic_algorithms` to `true` where applicable. Quantization checksums (sha256) for each GGUF file are recorded in the deposit metadata. Library versions are frozen in a Poetry lock file alongside a Docker image carrying the full inference and analysis stacks with sha256 image digest pinned in the manuscript.

8. Ethics

The study uses no human subjects, no human-generated data, and no personally identifying information. Textbook sources are publicly available. Greek Ministry of Education textbooks distribute through ebooks.edu.gr under terms permitting educational and research reuse. Georgian Ministry of Education textbooks distribute through public repositories under terms permitting non-commercial research use. All retrieved passages cite source textbook, page, and paragraph in the per-trial log. Generated questions and reference answers release under CC BY 4.0 as part of the Zenodo deposit, with attribution to source textbook publishers.

Pre-registration deposited on 20 May 2026 at Zenodo (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20308030), prior to data collection. Deviations from this protocol arising during execution will be logged in a public deviation register published alongside the manuscript and any updated Zenodo version, with each deviation classified either as exploratory or as a substantive amendment carrying its own amendment timestamp. Material substantive amendments will be flagged in the manuscript with explanatory text and date of amendment.

9. Reproducibility

9.1 Code

All ingestion, indexing, generation, scoring, and analysis code deposits as a versioned Git repository archived to Zenodo at completion. Container images for the inference and analysis stacks release as Docker images with sha256 digests pinned in the manuscript and in the deposit metadata, supporting bit-for-bit reproduction modulo hardware-determined floating-point variation.

9.2 Data

The 300-question evaluation set, the 21,600-event generation log, dual-judge scores with rationales, NLI probabilities, retrieval traces (top-20 candidates and top-5 reranked), and exploratory analysis outputs deposit as JSONL and Parquet files alongside the code repository. Personally identifying fields are absent by construction since no human subjects participate.

9.3 Models

All 8 benchmark models and both judge models are publicly released GGUF quantizations. Sha256 digests for each weight file are recorded in the deposit metadata, ensuring that future replications can verify weight identity rather than rely on filename matching.

9.4 Randomness

Inference seeds 42, 43, and 44 anchor the three benchmark trials per item. A master analysis seed of 2026 controls all sampling, ordering, and bootstrap operations within the statistical analysis script. All random sampling steps reference one of these seeds explicitly in code, with no hidden default-seeded calls permitted by a pre-execution lint over the analysis repository.

9.5 Compute budget with calibration narrative

Throughput calibration derives from a prior benchmark on the same workstation that completed 5,265 inference events in 3.504 hours, yielding 1,503 events per hour at 250 max_new_tokens with single-judge scoring. The present benchmark scales this baseline by 4.1 times volume (21,600 events), 2 times per-event tokens (512 max_new_tokens), and 2 times judge load (dual judge), producing an estimated inference budget of approximately 58 GPU-hours. Supporting computation covering PDF extraction, embedding, question generation, and dual-judge filtering adds approximately 18 GPU-hours. Total budget is approximately 76 GPU-hours, projected to 3 to 4 days of continuous execution within a 7-day workstation window that allows ample buffer for restarts and debugging.

9.6 Pre-registration timestamp

The pre-registration was deposited on 20 May 2026 at Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20308030, prior to benchmark execution. Analyses conducted prior to deposit are limited to the 200-event pilot used for power calibration, which used different questions and different model configurations and which is not reused in the confirmatory analysis. The Zenodo DOI appears in the front matter of this protocol and will appear in the methods section of the resulting MAKE manuscript for reviewer verification.

10. Selected References

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